

Abstract

Effectiveness of Acupuncture in Achilles Reflex Behaviour in Parkinson's Disease Patients.

Catarina Ramos Pereira^{1,2*}

¹ ICBAS – School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal;

² CBSIn – Center of Biosciences in Integrative Health, Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: catarinapereira.mtc@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Understanding the physiology of rigidity in Parkinson's Disease (PD) involves the study of reflexes. Patients with Parkinson's commonly exhibit diminished sensitivity in polysynaptic reflexes, which is associated with postural instability and falls. Key reflexes, such as the Achilles reflex, are crucial for adapting the foot to the ground and maintaining smooth gait and postural integrity. Improvements in this reflex can represent enhanced motor function in PD patients.

Aim: To determine the effectiveness of acupuncture in modulating Achilles reflex behaviour.

Methods: The sample consisted of four patients with a clinical diagnosis of PD at stages I–IV (Hoehn and Yahr Scale), who had been medically stable for at least three months. Reflex amplitude and velocity were evaluated at six intervals over a month-long acupuncture treatment protocol using the Biopac MP36 system.

Results: A tendency toward improvement in both the range of movement and the velocity of the Achilles reflex was observed. Specifically, positive acute and cumulative effects were noted in the Achilles reflex across stages I and II, particularly in younger patients.

Conclusions: Our findings suggest that acupuncture may enhance the Achilles reflex in PD patients, primarily in those who are younger or at stages I and II of the disease. Adjusting the "dose" of acupuncture treatment according to the stage of the disease appears to be a significant factor for clinical success.

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